

Correlative Study of ACR-TIRADS (2017) with Histopathological Evaluation of Thyroid Nodules in a Peripheral Medical College in West Bengal

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Abstract:

Background: Thyroid swelling is a common clinical finding with a quiet high prevalence among Indian population. Risk stratification of these thyroid swellings into benign and malignant hence become a crucial part in the management of these cases. Here comes the role of ultrasonography, with its added benefits of portability, cost effectiveness, lack of ionizing radiations and non-invasiveness. To standardize ultrasound findings Thyroid Imaging Recording and Data System (TIRADS) classification are used.

Methods: History and physical examination were done in all cases of thyroid nodule. Serum TSH, T3, T4, pre and post operative calcium on post operative day 3 were done in all cases. Ultrasonography and fine needle aspiration Cytology (FNAC)/ultrasonography guided if nodule size less than 1cm were done in all cases. All patients underwent surgical intervention, and specimens were sent for Histopathology examinations.

Result: Common age groups were 25 to 44 years, and more than 80% cases were female. 65% cases were less than TIRADS 4 and 35% cases were more than TIRADS 4. Patients with TIRADS score of 4 and more were having higher chance of being suspected with malignancy on histopathology examination than the patients with score of less than 4. On the basis of sonographic findings, half of the subjects among solid components were found to be having malignancy, whereas, more than half of the subjects with micro-calcifications were having malignancy and all the subjects with irregular margins were diagnosed with malignancy on HPE.

Conclusions: Thyroid ultrasound plays a key role in diagnosis, and it allows for the morphological characterization of Thyroid nodules, thereby facilitating adequate selection of those nodules amenable to FNAB cytological diagnosis. There is paucity of data regarding TIRADS score and its relationship with thyroid pathology in this part of the world. This study was an honest attempt to fill this gap, which would be helpful in managing the thyroid disorder more efficiently and will be convenient for risk stratification.

Keywords: Thyroid nodule, Ultrasonography, TIRADS, Histopathology.

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Introduction

Thyroid swelling is a common presentation with majority of these being benign diseases, of which goiter is the commonest and a few are malignant. The magnitude of problem in Southeast Asia is estimated to be around 172 million with goiters and iodine deficiency is estimated to be around 600 million. [1] It has been estimated that about 42 mil-

lion people in India suffer from thyroid diseases. [2] Thyroid swellings are common clinical findings and have a reported prevalence of 4% to 7% in the adult population. [3] Discrete thyroid swellings are common and are present in 8.5% population in India. [3] Thyroid swellings are four times more common in females.

Ultrasonography is an important component in the work up of thyroid nodules. [4] Ultrasonography provides advantages including portability, cost effectiveness, lack of ionizing radiations and non-invasiveness. Hence clinical suspicion when coupled with ultrasound features, to a great extent, can categorize the patients into high risk or low risk. In a developing country like India, where patient load is high and manpower available in healthcare is proportionally low, cost effectiveness is very important. Thus, ultrasound renders an important role in evaluation of thyroid nodule. To standardize ultrasound findings Thyroid Imaging Recording and Data System (TIRADS) classification can be used. This study aims to assess the accuracy of TIRADS classification in the evaluation of thyroid swellings by comparing with final histopathological reports.

TIRADS classification [5] (American College of Radiology)

Thyroid Imaging and Reporting System (TIRADS)

Figure1: American College of Radiology TIRADS point distribution

- TIRADS1 (0POINTS)–benign gland
- TIRADS2 (2POINTS) –not suspicious
- TIRADS3 (3POINTS)–mildly suspicious
- TIRADS4 (4-6POINTS)-moderately Suspicious
- TIRADS5 (MORETHAN 7) –probably malignant

Among the sonological features, some features point towards malignancy.

Suspicious sonological factors [7] are

was proposed similar to BIRADS classification. The classification system is used to differentiate thyroid swellings into benign or malignant without invasive procedures, based on ultrasound evaluation of thyroid using suspicious sonographic features. It was first proposed by Horvath E [6] in 2009. Later different variants of TIRADS came with some modifications in grading system. In the present study we are using TIRADS classification as proposed by American College of Radiology (2017). In this system for assessing a nodule, one feature is selected from each of the first four categories and all the features that apply from the final category (echogenic foci) and the points are summed up. The points total determines the nodule's ACR TI-RADS level, which ranges from TR1 (benign) to TR5 (high suspicion of malignancy).

Classification

- Solid components
- Hypoechogenicity
- Micro calcification
- Taller than wider
- Irregular margins

Aims and objectives

1. To determine the background characteristics of the patients with thyroid swelling admitted for thyroid surgery in the wards of Department of ENT, North Bengal Medical College Hospital.

- To assess the TIRADS score and its association with histopathology findings and sonographic features of the study subjects.

Materials and Methods

An observational, descriptive study with cross sectional design was conducted. The study was conducted in the wards of the Department of ENT of North Bengal Medical College and Hospital, one of the peripheral Medical Colleges of West Bengal located near Siliguri town of Darjeeling district. Necessary data for the study were collected from January 2019 to September 2020.

Study Techniques

- Interview of the study subjects using the pre-designed Thyroid Questionnaire.⁸
- Physical examination of thyroid nodule which includes inspection, palpation and auscultation, and clinical examination like general body built, pulse, eyes, presence of fine tremors, skin changes and presence of lymph nodes if any.

- Laboratory investigation which includes serum TSH, T3, T4, pre and post operative calcium on post operative day 3.
- Ultrasonography (done by same Radiologist to bring uniformity to results).
- Fine needle aspiration Cytology (FNAC)/ultrasonography guided if nodule size less than 1cm.
- All patients underwent surgical intervention on case-to-case basis which included hemithyroidectomy, total and completion thyroidectomy.
- Specimen was subjected to Histopathology examination.

Results

The study was conducted among 60 Patients with thyroid swelling. The result sections have been described below

Table1: Distribution of study subjects according to age (n=60)

Age(years)	Frequency	Percentage
15-24	8	13.3
25-34	21	35.0
35-44	17	28.3
45-54	11	18.3
≥55	3	5.1
Total	60	100.0

Table 1 shows that majority of the patients were in 25-34 years of age group (35%), followed by 35-44 years (28.3%),45-54 years (18.3%),15-24 years (13.3%) and 55 years or more (5.1%). The mean (SD) age of the patients was 36.02 (10.09) years.

Figure2: Distribution of study subjects according to age (n=60)

Table2: Distribution of study subjects according to sex (n=60)

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
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Male	11	18.3
Female	49	81.7
Total	60	100.0

Table 2 shows that 81.7% of the patients were female and 18.3% were males.

Table3: Distribution of study subjects according to age and sex (n=60)

Age(years)	Sex n (row percentage)		Chi square value(df), p value
	Male	Female	
12-24	0	8 (100)	10.054 (4) 0.040
25-34	5 (23.8)	16 (76.2)	
35-44	1 (5.9)	16 (94.1)	
45-54	5 (45.5)	6 (54.5)	
≥55	0	3 (100)	
Total	11 (18.3)	49 (81.7)	

A table 3 shows that among the age group of the 15-24 years and 55 years or more, all the subjects was females, and the proportions of females were more among the rest of age groups. These differences among proportions were statistically significant (*p value*-0.040).

Figure3: Distribution of study subjects according to age and sex (n=60)

Table4: Distribution of study subjects according to TIRADS score ((n=60)

TIRADS score	Frequency	Percentage
<4	39	65.0
≥4	21	35.0
Total	60	100.0

Table 4 shows that 35% of the patients had TIRADS score of 4 and above.

Figure4: Distribution of study subjects according to TIRADSs core ((n=60)

Table 5: Risk ratio of malignancy suspected on Histopathology examination by TIRADS score (n=60)

TIRADS score	Malignancy No/Yes		Total	Odds ratio (95% CI)
<4	39	-	39	Reference
≥4	08	13	21	2.652 (1.522-4.528)
Total	47	13	60	

Table 5 shows that patients with TIRADS score of 4 and more were having 2.652 times higher chance (95% CI-1.522-4.528) of being suspected with malignancy on histopathology examination than the patients with score of less than 4.

Table 6: Distribution of study subjects according to malignancy on HPE by suspicious sonographic features (n=60)

Sonographic parameter	Malignancy on HPE		Total*
	No	Yes	
Solid component	09	09	18
Hypo-echogenecity	11	7	21
Micro-calcification	6	8	14
Irregular margins	-	8	8

*Multiple responses

Table 6 shows that on the basis of sonographic findings, half of the subjects among solid components were found to be having malignancy, whereas, more than half of the subjects with micro-calcifications were having malignancy and all the

subjects with irregular margins were diagnosed with malignancy on HPE. None of the subjects were detected with taller than wide features on sonography.

Table 7: Distribution of study subjects according to malignancy on HPE by TIRADS score (n=60)

TIRADS score	Malignancy on HPE		Total	Chi-square value (df), p value
	No	Yes		
0-1	01(100)	-	01(100)	36.432 (4), <0.001
2	21(100)	-	21 (100)	
3	17(100)	-	17 (100)	
4-6	08 (50)	08 (50)	16 (100)	
≥7	-	05(100)	05 (100)	

Table7 shows that subjects with score of 4-6 were having 50% cases of malignancy and score of seven and more were having 100 score of malignancy, and these difference in proportions were statistically significant (p value <0.001).

Discussion

The present study uses the TIRADS classification of American college of Radiology, which assigns a thyroid pathology TIRADS-Level of TR 1-5. In this regard, a high probability of malignancy is

considered from level 4, and FNAC is advised in the case of thyroid nodules with TI-RADS level 3 and 5.

The mean (SD) age of the patients in our study was 36.02 (10.09) years. Majority of the patients were in 25-34 years of age group followed by 35-44 years and majority of the patients were females.

Joanna Grace Dy et al [9] in their study "Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System (TIRADS) in Stratifying Risk of Thyroid Malignancy at The Medical City" conducted among 149 patients with thyroid nodules observed that majority of patients were in their 30s (23%), 40s (22%), or 50s (22%) and majority of the patients were females, which corresponds with our study findings.

In our study among the age group of the 15-24 years and 55 years or more, all the subjects were females, and the proportions of females were more among the rest of age groups. These differences among proportions were statistically significant (p value=0.040).

Sharath Chandra BJ et al [10] on their study "Comparison of TIRADS [Thyroid imaging reporting and data system] with histopathology in assessment of thyroid nodules" conducted among 82 patients presenting with clinically palpable thyroid nodules reported that 85.4% were females whereas 14.6% were male patients in the study. The present study corroborates with the observations reported by Sharath Chandra BJ et al.

Kaseb H et al [11] in their study reported that majority of the patients were females (65%), which also is similar to our study findings.

The mean (SD) and median (Inter-quartile range) of TIRAD score of the subject were 3.42 (1.61) and 3(2, 4.75) respectively and 35% of the patients had TIRAD score of 4 and above. C. García-Moncó Fernández et al [12] found that 24.2% of the subjects were having detected malignancy among the patients with TIRAD score of 4 and more, which corresponds with our study with 21.7% of the subjects were diagnosed to have malignant findings, the patients with TIRAD score of 4 and above were having higher proportions of malignancy suspected on histopathology examination than score of less than 4, this association was statistically significant (p value <0.001)

The present study found that the TIRAD score of 4 and more were having 2.652 times higher chance (95%CI - 1.522-4.528) of being suspected with malignancy on histopathology examination than the patients with score of less than 4. Grace Dy et al observe similar findings, where they reported higher odds of being suspected with malignancy on TIRAD score of 4 and more.

Our study found that subjects with score of 4-6

were having 50% cases of malignancy and score of seven and more were having 100 score of malignancy and these difference in proportions were statistically significant (p value <0.001).

Kwak et al. [13] showed that the malignancy risk of TIRADS (TIRADS by Kwak-2011) category 3, 4a, 4b, 4c and 5 were 12.5% (1 out of 8), 12.82% (5 out of 39), 26.19% (11 out of 42), 53.70% (29 out of 54) and 66.67% (4 out of 6) respectively.

On the basis of sonographic findings, half of the subjects among solid components were found to be having malignancy, whereas, more than half of the subjects with micro-calcifications were having malignancy and all the subjects with irregular margins were diagnosed with malignancy on HPE.

Subjects with score of 4-6 were having 50% cases of malignancy and score of seven and more were having 100 score of malignancy, and these difference in proportions were statistically significant (p value <0.001).

Conclusion

Thyroid gland nodules in themselves are not a disease entity; rather, they are the physical expression of a broad range of thyroid disorders. Thyroid ultrasound plays a key role in this regard, since it allows for the morphological characterization of Thyroid nodules, thereby facilitating adequate selection of those nodules amenable to FNAB cytological diagnosis. There is paucity of data regarding TIRADS score and its relationship with thyroid pathology in this part of the world. This study was an honest attempt to fill this gap, which would be helpful in managing the thyroid disorder more efficiently and will be convenient for risk stratification.

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